

TRANSLATION AND ITS TYPES

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Annotation. This article describes the main types of translation, classifications of scientists by translation. Also, its role in not only Uzbek, but also world literature was discussed, and the names of Uzbek translators who contributed to the development of this field were noted.

Key words. Translation, translators, oral translation, written translation, consecutive translation, simultaneous translation, literary translation, informative translation, classification, interpretation.

TARJIMA VA UNING TURLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tarjimaning asosiy turlari, olimlarning tarjima bo'yicha klassifikatsiyalari bayon qilingan. Shuningdek, uning nafaqat o'zbek, balki jahon adabiyotida tutgan o'rni muhokama qilingan, bu soha rivojiga hissa qo'shgan o'zbek tarjimonlari nomlari qayd etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Tarjima, tarjimonlar, og'zaki tarjima, yozma tarjima, ketma-ket tarjima, sinxron tarjima, badiiy tarjima, infarmatsion tarjima, tasnif, talqin.

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Аннотация. В данной статье описаны основные виды перевода, классификации ученых по переводу. Также обсуждалась его роль не только в узбекской, но и мировой литературе, и отмечались имена узбекских переводчиков, внесших свой вклад в развитие этой области.

Ключевые слова. Перевод, переводчики, устный перевод, письменный перевод, последовательный перевод, синхронный перевод, художественный перевод, информативный перевод, классификация, устный перевод.

Translation is a tool that serves the interests of friendship, fraternity and cooperation between different peoples, and the expansion of economic-political, scientific, cultural and literary relations between them.

Translation accelerates the process of interaction and influence of literature of different nations. Thanks to translated works, people can enjoy masterpieces of world literature. Translation, as a necessary tool for the development of languages, improves the pace of their development, increases vocabulary, enriches a person's spiritual life, realizes the possibilities of the mother tongue, makes it more beautiful. Moreover, the reader's thinking is sharpened and enriched with new ideas and concepts. Translation serves to establish new attitudes and views in society as well as having a positive effect on the culture and spirituality of different peoples. It is a factor of organization and improvement of intercultural communication.

According to G.Salomov, the term "Tarjima"("translation") was changed to Arabic from the Persian word "tarzabon", and tarzabon means "a beautiful speaker, eloquent person" in Persian.

In Arabic, this word is in the form of "tarjumon", from which "tarjima" or "tarjuma" is derived.¹²

In the Uzbek language, it is expressed by the terms "o'tkazish"("transfer"), "qaytarish"("return"), "ag'darish"("overturn"), "o'girish"("turn").

Uzbek readers have been familiar with the works of English-speaking authors since the 30s of the 20th century. These works were translated into Uzbek mainly through Russian. In the 20th century, famous translator-writers such as Cholpon, Oybek, Gafur Ghulam, Shaikhzoda, Kadir Mirmuhammedov, Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov, Ibrahim Gafurov came to the world and translated the best works of famous representatives of world literature into Uzbek language. This good tradition is successfully continued by the translators organized around the "World Literature" magazine during the period of independence.

It is essential to mention that a generation of translators, who can skillfully translate not only from the Russian language, but also directly from the languages of the Western and Eastern nations into Uzbek, has appeared. Among them, A. Faizulla -

¹² G'.Salomov "Introduction to the theory of translation" "Reader" publishing house Tashkent -1978

Hindi-Urdu, A. Kochiboyev - French, M. Saidumarov - Arabic, M. Azam and B. Sharipov - Turkish, U. Kochkar - Azerbaijani, M. Akbarov and Ya. Egamova - with the translations made from German languages, has given "world cultural heritage" to Uzbek nation.

In translation studies, different types of translation can be distinguished depending on the form of the material in the original language and the translated language. This is the basis for the first classification.

L. S. Barkhudarov distinguishes four main types of translation according to the form in which the original language and the translated language text are presented:

1) oral-oral; 2) written-written; 3) oral-written; 4) written-oral. Among these types of translation, oral-oral translation is divided into 2 types: 1) consecutive; 2) oral simultaneous.¹³

V. N. Komissarov's translation classification is as follows:

- literary translation;
- informative translation.¹⁴

Each type of translation has its own combination of factors influencing the translating process. The general theory of translation should be supplemented by a number of special translation theories identifying major types of translation activities and describing the predominant features of each type.

Different types of translation can be singled out depending on the predominant communicative function of the source text or the form of speech involved in the translation process. Thus we can distinguish between literary and informative translation, on the one hand, and between **written** and **oral translation (or interpretation)**, on the other hand.

¹³ L. S. Barhudarov. - Moskva, 1975. National Library of Poland NUKAT Center of Warsaw University Library.

¹⁴ Komissarov V.N. Korolova A.L. A Manual of translation from English into Russian M., Higher school, 1990.

In written translation the source text is in written form, as is the target text. In oral translation or interpretation the interpreter listens to the oral presentation of the original and translates it as an oral message in translating language. As a result, in the first case the Receptor of the translation can read it while in the second case he hears it.

Literary translation deals with literary texts, i.e. works of fiction or poetry whose main function is to make an emotional or aesthetic impression upon the reader. Their communicative value depends, first and foremost, on their artistic quality and the translator’s primary task is to reproduce this quality in translation.

Literary translation consists of the translation:

- poetry
- plays,
- literary books,
- literary texts,
- songs,
- rhymes,
- literary articles,
- fiction novels,
- novels,
- short stories,
- poems, etc.

Informative translation is rendering into the target language non-literary texts, the main purpose of which is to convey a certain amount of ideas, to inform the reader. However, if the source text is of some length, its translation can be listed as literary or informative only as an approximation. A literary text may, in fact, include some parts of purely informative character. Contrariwise, informative translation may comprise some elements aimed at achieving an aesthetic effect.¹⁵ This includes all information related to business, science, daily-living, and social and political activities.

Above, translation and its importance and its types, classifications of scholars, place of translation in Uzbek literature and experienced Uzbek translators were briefly discussed. Through this analysis, we would like to convey to the reader the main concepts of translation theory. It is necessary to fill up the scientific works on this topic and take a deeper approach.

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